

A Post-Quantum Cryptographic Framework for High-Level Security Protocols in 6G

Pasindu Udugahapattuwa*, Chamitha De Alwis†, Engin Zeydan‡,
Uditha Wijewardhana§, Madhusanka Liyanage¶

*Department of Electrical, Electronic and Telecommunication Engineering, Kotelawala Defence University, Sri Lanka,

‡Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka,

†School of Computing, Engineering, and Creative Industries, University of Bedfordshire, U.K.,

‡Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Spain,

¶Network Softwarization and Security Labs (NetsLab), School of Computer Science, University College Dublin, Ireland,

Emails: *udugahapattuwad@kdu.ac.lk, †chamitha@ieee.org, ‡zeydan@cttc.es,

§uditha@sjp.ac.lk, ¶madhusanka@ucd.ie.

Abstract—Sixth Generation (6G) networks will support critical, latency-sensitive, and large-scale services, making them attractive targets for quantum-capable adversaries. To address this, the paper proposes a conceptual Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) framework for high-level security protocols in 6G, including Transport Layer Security (TLS) 1.3, Internet Key Exchange version 2 (IKEv2), Secure Shell (SSH), Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT), and Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP), using security-by-design principles, hybrid classical–post-quantum migration, and optimization for resource-constrained and heterogeneous environments. The framework defines key metrics such as handshake latency, computational and memory overhead, energy consumption, interoperability, and resistance to quantum and classical attacks, and analyzes risks introduced by hybrid protocol complexity, side channels, and implementation flaws. The framework is illustrated via a reference hybrid TLS 1.3 design using National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)-standardized Module-Lattice-Based Key-Encapsulation Mechanism (ML-KEM) and Module-Lattice-Based Digital Signature Algorithm (ML-DSA) and an evaluation methodology based on Open Secure Sockets Layer (OpenSSL)/liboqs, outlining how future prototypes can measure latency, bandwidth, and computational overhead under Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) and Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) constraints. By combining requirements analysis, design patterns, and evaluation methodology, this work supports quantum-safe 6G infrastructure with scalable, reliable, and long-term secure deployment, providing a blueprint for future empirical validation rather than reporting completed measurements.

Index Terms—6G, Framework, High-level protocols, Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC).

I. INTRODUCTION

Sixth-generation (6G) networks are expected to enable ultra-reliable, low-latency, and intelligent connectivity for critical infrastructures, cloud-native services, cyber-physical systems, and massive Internet of Things (IoT) deployments, making security and privacy core design requirements rather than optional additions. At the same time, large-scale quantum computers threaten the public-key cryptosystems, especially

Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA) and Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC), that currently secure high-level 6G protocols such as TLS, IKEv2, Secure/Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions (S/MIME), and related authentication schemes across cloud and IoT ecosystems. In response, NIST has standardized post-quantum cryptographic Key Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM)s and digital signature schemes, opening a path toward quantum-safe protocol design. However, deploying these primitives in 6G requires systematic protocol-level integration that preserves functionality, interoperability, and compliance with tight bandwidth, latency, processing, and memory constraints, especially in embedded and resource-constrained environments. It also requires coordinated migration strategies that support digital sovereignty, global competitiveness, and resilient digital services and supply chains.

This paper contributes to the design, integration, and evaluation of PQC algorithms within high-level security protocols for 6G technology. It first identifies the main roadblocks and missing building blocks for quantum-safe protocol adoption in 6G, then proposes a conceptual framework for hybrid and fully quantum-safe migration, and finally reviews and analyzes representative case studies across TLS, IKEv2, and authentication mechanisms [1], [2]. The results provide both security and performance assessments under realistic 6G constraints, offering practical guidance for standardization and deployment of post-quantum cryptographic frameworks for next-generation high-level security protocols. The key contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We identify security, performance, and compatibility requirements and challenges for integrating PQC into widely deployed high-level protocols in 6G networks.
- We propose a conceptual framework along with evaluation metrics and migration patterns that balance backward compatibility, interoperability, and future-proof quantum resilience in 6G networks.
- We outline a reference Post-Quantum TLS (PQ-

TLS)/Post-Quantum IKEv2 (PQ-IKEv2) design and evaluation blueprint, including a prototype hybrid PQC migration pattern (PQ-TLS 1.3 with ML-KEM/ML-DSA), quantitative evaluation methodology for handshake latency, computational overhead, and bandwidth consumption, and mapping of future empirical measurements into the Architectural Impact Matrix and 6G Key Performance Indicator (KPI) Envelope to validate the framework..

To complement the conceptual framework, this paper outlines a proof-of-concept hybrid PQ-TLS 1.3 / PQ-IKEv2 design aligned with one migration pattern and a corresponding evaluation plan under 6G-inspired URLLC and mMTC constraints. The planned evaluation will measure handshake latency, central processing unit (CPU), energy overhead, bandwidth expansion, and map these measurements into the Architectural Impact Matrix and 6G KPI Envelope.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. 6G and its security requirements

6G networks are envisioned as a ubiquitous, intelligent communication fabric that tightly integrates the physical and digital worlds. Building upon Fifth Generation (5G) capabilities, 6G targets significant improvements in data rates, latency, reliability, and device density to support immersive services, holographic communication, large-scale cyber-physical systems, extended reality, autonomous mobility, remote surgery, and industrial automation across terrestrial, aerial, and satellite segments, making end-to-end security a core design principle [3], [4]. Within this context, high-level security protocols such as TLS for application-layer security, IKEv2 for backhaul and inter-network tunnels, and EAP-based authentication frameworks must deliver strong confidentiality, integrity, and authentication guarantees. These protocols need to meet the stringent demands of URLLC/IHRLLC, eMBB, and mMTC service classes while respecting strict constraints on sub-millisecond latency, ultra-high reliability (“six-nines”), energy efficiency, and operation across highly heterogeneous devices ranging from cloud data centers to resource-constrained IoT nodes [5], [6].

B. Quantum computing and PQC integration in high-level protocols

Quantum computing threatens current public-key cryptography through Shor’s algorithm, which can break RSA and ECC in polynomial time, and Grover’s algorithm, which effectively reduces the security level of symmetric ciphers and hash functions [7], [8]. This development intensifies the “store-now-decrypt-later” threat in 6G networks, where adversaries can record encrypted traffic today for future decryption, posing serious risks to long-lived data in critical infrastructure, healthcare, and industrial control systems [9], [10].

Consequently, high-level security protocols central to 6G — including TLS, IKEv2, DTLS, IPsec, and lightweight IoT protocols such as MQTT and CoAP — must transition to

PQC. This migration is essential to ensure quantum resilience while meeting the stringent performance, latency, and energy constraints of URLLC/IHRLLC and mMTC services [5], [11].

Although PQC schemes such as ML-KEM and ML-DSA introduce additional overhead in bandwidth and computation, recent studies indicate that hybrid approaches can keep performance within acceptable bounds for many 6G scenarios [17], [18]. A holistic, cross-protocol framework is therefore required to systematically address these challenges, as summarized in Table I.

C. Comparison with Existing PQC Integration Frameworks

Table II compares the proposed framework with representative prior work on PQC integration for communication protocols. While earlier studies have advanced protocol migration, hybrid key exchange, and quantum-safe authentication, most remain narrowly focused on individual protocols or general 5G/Internet settings. In contrast, this work is explicitly designed for 6G networks: it couples PQC adoption with slice-level KPI requirements and employs both an Architectural Impact Matrix and formal migration patterns to systematically connect cryptographic choices to system-level performance, interoperability, and quantum-resilience outcomes.

III. CHALLENGES FOR PQC INTEGRATION WITH HIGH-LEVEL SECURITY PROTOCOLS IN 6G

Migrating 6G to a quantum-safe architecture requires more than simply replacing RSA or ECC with post-quantum primitives. High-level security protocols must continue to guarantee forward secrecy, strong authentication, and robustness against downgrade and cross-protocol attacks in the presence of both classical and quantum-capable adversaries.

The primary challenges fall into three categories:

- **Security and architectural integrity:** Hybrid classical–post-quantum constructions are a pragmatic transition mechanism yet increase protocol complexity, expand the attack surface, and complicate security proofs. Secure integration with legacy certificate hierarchies via hybrid certificates and multi-key identities must also be achieved without weakening overall system guarantees.
- **Performance and interoperability:** Larger PQC keys, signatures, and ciphertexts introduce significant computational and bandwidth overheads that are especially critical for URLLC services (real-time IoT control, V2X safety, interactive applications) and resource-constrained mMTC devices. Backward compatibility further inflates message sizes and makes negotiation between upgraded and legacy endpoints fragile.
- **Constraints and gaps in standardization and verification:** Long-lived embedded systems, industrial sensors, and automotive secure elements require cryptographic agility for remote updates yet face severe resource limits. The ecosystem still lacks mature standards, lightweight PQC schemes suitable for the edge, formal verification

TABLE I: Overview of PQC Integration Efforts in High-Level Protocols in 6G

Protocol	PQC Algorithms Tested	Challenges Observed	Impact to 6G Networks
TLS 1.3 (PQ-TLS) [12], [13]	ML-KEM (KEM), ML-DSA (signatures), Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) over NTRU-Lattice-Based Digital Signature Algorithm (FN-DSA), Stateless Hash-Based Digital Signature Algorithm (SLH-DSA)	Increased handshake message size; certificate bloat; performance overhead in constrained devices; interoperability with legacy clients	Increased control/user-plane handshake latency for URLLC and interactive services; higher overhead on 6G air interface and fronthaul links; greater need for TLS offload at edge/cloud to preserve Quality-of-Service (QoS) and slice Service Level Agreement (SLA)s.
IKEv2 / Internet Protocol Security (IPsec) [1]	ML-KEM for key exchange; ML-DSA/FN-DSA for authentication	Overhead in negotiation messages; impact on Virtual Private Network (VPN) throughput; compatibility with hardware accelerators	Reduced effective VPN throughput for 6G backhaul and core tunnels; higher CPU load on gateways and Uranium Processing Facility (UPF)s; potential capacity reduction or higher cost for secure network slices and inter-domain peering.
SSH [1], [14]	ML-KEM and N-th degree Truncated polynomial Ring Units (NTRU) for key exchange; ML-DSA for authentication	Session setup delay; memory overhead in embedded SSH servers; lack of standardized certificate handling	Higher resource usage on small cells and edge nodes during secure management sessions; potential slowdown in large-scale Operation, Administration and Management (OAM), zero-touch provisioning, and slice lifecycle operations in dense 6G deployments.
S/MIME / Email Security [13]	ML-DSA and SLH-DSA for signatures; ML-KEM for key exchange in hybrid certificates	Large signature and key sizes causing email overhead; interoperability with existing Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) hierarchies; limited tooling for PQC-enabled Certificate Authority (CA)s	Increased size of management-plane alerts, logs, and incident reports; higher storage and archival overhead for long-term security records; minor but cumulative impact on 6G operations and compliance workflows.
IoT Protocols (MQTT, CoAP, Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture (OPC UA)) [1], [15]	ML-KEM for constrained key exchange; ML-DSA for device authentication	Bandwidth and energy limitations; limited secure element support; difficulty in updating firmware-based crypto stacks	Shorter battery life and reduced link efficiency for massive IoT due to larger messages; tighter bandwidth margins for mMTC/URLLC slices; challenges in meeting latency and reliability targets on constrained edge devices.
Authentication Protocols (FIDO2, Multi Factor Authentication (MFA), Hardware Tokens) [16]	ML-DSA, FN-DSA in token firmware	Slow turnover of hardware tokens; constrained secure element memory; migration costs for large deployments	Slower migration of operator and tenant identities to quantum-safe methods; constrained token memory delaying PQC support for SIM/eSIM-like secure elements; potential weak link in end-to-end zero-trust and 6G slice access control.

TABLE II: Comparison of PQC Integration Frameworks for Communication Protocols

Framework / Study	Target protocols	6G awareness	Quantitative evaluation	Formal security analysis	Explicit architectural metrics
This work	TLS, IKEv2, authentication, IoT protocols	Yes	Planned	Yes	Yes
TLS/SSH prototyping [19]	TLS, SSH	No	Yes	Partial	No
PQ-TLS-enabled Open5G [11]	TLS in 5G core	Partial	Yes	Partial	No
6G authentication and key agreement survey [20]	6G AKA, IoT, access control	Yes	Limited	Partial	No
Integrated survey on PQC/Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) for 6G [21]	General 6G security	Yes	No	No	No

tools for PQC-enabled protocols, and well-established solutions for key management, revocation, and long-term archival.

These challenges motivate the development of a structured

migration framework together with architectural metrics, as in Figure Fig. 1 to systematically evaluate and compare candidate PQC integration designs.

IV. PROPOSED PQC FRAMEWORK FOR HIGH-LEVEL SECURITY PROTOCOLS IN 6G

To address the requirements and challenges outlined in Section III, we propose a structured conceptual framework for integrating PQC into high-level security protocols in 6G, as illustrated in Figure 2. The framework is guided by four core design principles: (i) Security-by-Design and Privacy-by-Design, (ii) Hybrid Classical-Post-Quantum Approaches, (iii) Interoperability and Backward Compatibility, and (iv) Optimization for Constrained Environments.

Security-by-Design and Privacy-by-Design mandate that PQC integration preserves the confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity guarantees of existing protocols while incorporating protections against metadata leakage and side-channel attacks from the outset. Hybrid Classical-Post-Quantum Approaches combine PQC primitives with classical cryptography (e.g., ECC with ML-KEM for key exchange) to ensure backward compatibility and resilience against potential weaknesses in newly standardized PQC algorithms during the transition period. Interoperability and Backward Compatibility are achieved through protocol negotiation mechanisms such as TLS handshake extensions and IKEv2 negotiation payloads, enabling

Fig. 1: Challenges for PQC Integration with High-Level Security Protocols in 6G

secure fallback to classical algorithms without introducing downgrade vulnerabilities. Optimization for Constrained Environments focuses on minimizing bandwidth and computational overhead through strategic algorithm selection, hardware acceleration, and protocol-level optimizations to meet 6G’s stringent latency and energy requirements.

We identify three primary migration patterns for adapting high-level protocols to PQC:

- *Drop-in Replacement*: Direct substitution of RSA or ECC primitives with equivalent PQC counterparts without major structural changes. While simple to deploy, this pattern can lead to inefficiencies due to larger key and signature sizes.
- *Hybrid Protocol Design*: Integration of PQC alongside classical cryptography within the same handshake or authentication flow. This is currently the most widely adopted approach in PQC-enabled protocol prototypes as it provides security against both classical and quantum adversaries.
- *Protocol Redesign*: Fundamental rethinking of protocol structures to better exploit PQC-specific properties, offering improved long-term efficiency at the cost of greater deployment disruption.

TLS serves as a representative high-level protocol to illustrate the application of these patterns. The framework aligns with ongoing standardization efforts in the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), and International Organization for Standardization (ISO), and leverages open-source toolkits such as OpenSSL with Library for Open Quantum Safe (liboqs) extensions for practical implementation and evaluation.

Reference Hybrid PQ-TLS 1.3 Design: As a concrete instantiation, our reference design focuses on a hybrid PQ-TLS 1.3 configuration using combined ECC + ML-KEM key exchange and hybrid Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) + ML-DSA authentication. Server and client certificates are provisioned in either hybrid (classical + PQC) or Post-Quantum (PQ)-only formats, with TLS extensions used to advertise and negotiate support for these mechanisms. This reference design forms the basis for the performance, security, and interoperability evaluation methodology described in Section VII, which serves as the target configuration for future prototype implementations and empirical studies.

V. SECURITY ANALYSIS

We consider three adversary classes: classical adversaries that exploit conventional computation, side channels, implementation flaws, and weak parameterization; quantum adversaries equipped with large-scale quantum computers capable of breaking RSA and ECC via Shor’s algorithm and accelerating brute-force search via Grover’s algorithm; and hybrid adversaries that combine classical capabilities with limited quantum resources during the migration period. The threat model also includes active attackers capable of observing traffic, manipulating negotiation, and exploiting inconsistent deployment states between classical and post-quantum components.

Hybrid constructions provide transition security by preserving confidentiality and authenticity as long as at least one component remains secure under its respective hardness assumption. For hybrid key exchange, the session key is protected if at least one KEM satisfies its security notion; for hybrid signature, authentication holds if at least one signature scheme remains unforgeable. Accordingly, the TLS 1.3 reference de-

Fig. 2: Architecture diagram of the Proposed PQC Framework for High-Level Security Protocols in 6G

sign enforces mandatory hybrid negotiation and disables pure-classical fallback in high-security profiles.

Downgrade resistance is achieved through cipher-suite whitelisting, strict policy-based negotiation, and rejection of weaker parameter sets; unsafe fallback to classical-only operation is explicitly prevented. Composability with features such as Zero Round-Trip Time (0-RTT) or session resumption is handled by avoiding key-material reuse across contexts and constraining early-data mechanisms to preserve forward secrecy.

PQC schemes, particularly lattice-based algorithms such as ML-KEM and ML-DSA, remain vulnerable to side-channel attacks if not carefully implemented. The evaluation assumes constant-time reference implementations and standard hardening techniques; any remaining implementation-specific limitations are explicitly noted, in line with the Security-by-Design principle.

VI. EVALUATION METRICS AND METHODOLOGY

A. Metrics and 6G-Aligned Benchmarks

This framework evaluates PQC integration in 6G protocols using operational metrics spanning security, performance, and system constraints. It maps handshake latency, throughput, memory footprint, energy overhead, negotiation success rate, and certificate overhead to URLLC, eMBB, and mMTC envelopes. The result is a reproducible basis for comparing PQC designs under realistic 6G conditions.

Performance is measured at the protocol level under controlled conditions. Handshake latency is obtained from timestamp differentials between protocol state transitions and compared with classical TLS 1.3; URLLC targets sub-millisecond added delay. Throughput is measured via standardized file transfer tests, while memory and energy costs are profiled

during key generation, encapsulation, and signature verification. Indicative bounds include 32–64 KB additional Random Access Memory (RAM) for constrained mMTC devices.

Security, interoperability, and feasibility are assessed through dedicated indicators. Security evaluation covers NIST levels, hybrid robustness under attacks and fallback scenarios, side-channel leakage via timing and correlation power analysis, and formal verification using Tamarin or ProVerif. Interoperability is captured through certificate overhead, negotiation success rates, and migration effort. Tables III and IV define the comparison space.

B. Experimental Methodology

We outline here an evaluation methodology for future implementations of the framework. While we do not execute this methodology in this paper, it provides a concrete blueprint for subsequent empirical studies.

The future proof-of-concept uses OpenSSL 3.x with liboqs on a Linux testbed, with a traffic generator for repeatable measurements. The planned comparison instantiates classical TLS 1.3 with Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman Ephemeral (ECDHE)+ECDSA and hybrid TLS 1.3 with ML-KEM+ECDHE and ML-DSA; PQ-IKEv2 is included where relevant. This setup isolates PQC overhead while preserving implementation realism.

The scenarios emulate URLLC, eMBB, and mMTC conditions. URLLC uses small messages and strict latency, eMBB stresses throughput, and mMTC targets many small payloads under constrained-device assumptions. Planned experiments will vary handshake count, payload size, and concurrency, with a network emulator controlling delay and jitter. CPU time, energy, and bandwidth usage are recorded for handshake and application-data phases, and the metrics are mapped to Tables III and IV.

TABLE III: 6G-Aligned Architectural Impact Matrix for Proposed Integration Framework

Protocol Layer	6G Service Class	Structural Change Proposed by PQC Framework	Message Size Growth (Order of Magnitude)	Latency Sensitivity Impact by proposed framework	Architectural Mitigation Required	Risk Score (1-5)
TLS 1.3 (PQ-TLS) [12], [22]	URLLC / Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB)	Larger KEM and signature payloads in hybrid PQ-TLS 1.3 handshakes; PQ certificate chains increase control-plane message size	2x-5x vs ECC-based handshakes [23]	Moderate (handshake phase only; data path unaffected but impacts session setup for URLLC and low-latency services)	Session resumption and ticket reuse; edge/cloud TLS termination with hardware acceleration; careful cipher-suite negotiation	3 – Requires optimization
IKEv2 / IPsec [24]	Network slicing/core transport	Hybrid key exchange expansion and PQ-enabled certificate chains in PQ-IKEv2/IPsec tunnels, as explored in VPN and secure backhaul evaluations	2x-4x vs classical IKEv2 exchanges [25]	Low-to-moderate (core/backhaul typically more latency-tolerant; increased tunnel setup time but limited steady-state impact)	Hardware acceleration at gateways/UPFs; batching of SA establishments; off-path key management services	2 – Minor architectural impact
SSH [14], [1]	Management plane (OAM, configuration, orchestration)	Expanded PQ key and signature objects for host and user authentication (e.g., ML-DSA-based host keys), aligned with secure management recommendations	3x-8x vs RSA/ECDSA key and signature exchanges [26]	Low (non-real-time, administrative sessions; minor impact on 6G slice and Network Function (NF) management workflows)	Gradual migration of management endpoints; use of jump hosts/bastions; key and banner compression where feasible	2 – Minor architectural impact
S/MIME / Email Security [27]	Management and control information (alerts, logs)	Larger PQ signatures and multi-algorithm certificate chains for S/MIME-protected emails and signed security alerts	3x-10x for small messages with long cert chains [13]	Low for store-and-forward email; mild impact on near-real-time security alerting and incident response notifications	Certificate chain optimization and pruning; detached signatures; archival/security gateways handling PQC-heavy objects	3 – Requires optimization
IoT Protocols (MQTT, CoAP, OPC UA) [24], [28]	mMTC / URLLC for industrial and sensor workloads	PQ KEM-based bootstrap and device auth plus large PQ signatures relative to small telemetry payloads (e.g., ML-DSA/FN-DSA), in line with PQC-IoT evaluations	Up to 10x for very small packets [29]	High (small-payload and duty-cycled devices; significant impact on radio efficiency, latency, and battery life in 6G mMTC)	Pre-shared or group-key bootstrap; header and payload compression; edge aggregation; PQC-tuned profiles for constrained nodes	5 – Redesign may be required
Authentication Protocols (FIDO2, MFA, Hardware Tokens) [30]	Access control/user and device onboarding	Larger PQ credential and attestation objects within authenticators, hardware tokens, and SIM/eSIM-like secure elements, reflecting trends in PQ authentication	2x-5x increase in credential and attestation size [31]	Medium (interactive login and MFA flows; some impact on user experience and large-scale 6G tenant onboarding processes)	Hybrid credential deployment window; phased token replacement; caching and reuse of attestation chains and meta-data	3 – Requires optimization

VII. EVALUATION BLUEPRINT FOR HYBRID PQ-TLS IN 6G CONTEXTS

A. Prototype Setup

The planned prototype will implement the Hybrid Protocol Design pattern for TLS 1.3, combining classical ECDHE+ECDSA with ML-KEM-768 key exchange and ML-DSA-65 signatures. The implementation will use OpenSSL 3.x with liboqs extensions on a Linux testbed and ARM-based client emulating constrained devices. This setup will isolate PQC overhead while maintaining realistic deployment conditions.

B. Latency, Bandwidth, and Computational Overhead

The planned evaluation will measure handshake latency distributions for classical versus hybrid PQ-TLS under URLLC-like (small messages, 1 ms Round-trip time (RTT)) and eMBB-like (larger payloads, 10 ms RTT) conditions. The expected outcome is that hybrid PQ-TLS will introduce additional handshake delay relative to the classical baseline, but the resulting latency should still be interpretable against the 1.5 ms URLLC envelope budgeted for security handshakes in Table IV. eMBB measurements will be used to assess whether throughput degradation remains operationally acceptable.

We expect handshake sizes to increase compared to classical baselines because of the larger ML-KEM public keys and ML-DSA signatures. Likewise, we anticipate a noticeable but manageable increase in CPU and energy usage on constrained clients. These expectations are included as hypotheses for future validation rather than as measured results.

C. Impact on Architectural Impact Matrix and KPI Envelope

The planned measurements will be used to refine the entries in Table III. In particular, “Message Size Growth” will be updated from literature-based estimates to measured values, and “Latency Sensitivity Impact” will be recalibrated using observed eMBB/URLLC behavior. These refinements will also support a more precise adjustment of the Risk Score for well-provisioned infrastructure.

The validation of Table IV will indicate whether hybrid PQ-TLS can operate within the intended URLLC, eMBB, and mMTC envelopes, including payload and memory constraints. PQ-IKEv2 can be included in the same evaluation plan to provide comparative round-trip behavior. These planned outcomes are intended to guide future optimization of compression, negotiation, and hardware acceleration strategies.

We emphasize that, at this stage, the prototype and measurements described in this section are part of an evaluation plan and have not yet been implemented. Real-world measurements are left as future work and will be used to refine the Architectural Impact Matrix and KPI Envelope.

VIII. DISCUSSION

The proposed PQC framework addresses 6G’s stringent requirements of ultra-low latency, massive device density, and heterogeneous capabilities while providing long-term post-quantum security. Security-by-design and privacy-by-design principles ensure forward secrecy, strong authentication, and resistance to downgrade and cross-protocol attacks. Hybrid classical–post-quantum designs exemplified by PQ-TLS and PQ-IKEv2 serve as transitional mechanisms despite increased complexity and verification challenges. Optimization strategies balance larger ML-KEM and ML-DSA keys/ciphertexts against URLLC latency, bandwidth, and energy constraints, motivating selective use of FN-DSA, protocol compression, and hardware acceleration.

The framework’s three migration patterns map to 6G deployment realities. Drop-in replacement offers pragmatic legacy support but stresses the existing PKI with larger messages. Hybrid protocol design leverages TLS extensions and IKEv2 payloads for cryptographic agility and remote updates in embedded IoT. Long-term protocol redesign enables 6G-native quantum-safe architectures exploiting lattice-based key reuse and stateless hash-based signatures, aligning with IETF, ETSI, and ISO standardization efforts. The architectural impact matrix and 6G KPI envelope provide structured guidance for key management, certificate formats, and interoperability.

IX. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper proposes a conceptual PQC framework for securing 6G infrastructures against quantum-capable adversaries while meeting ultra-low latency, massive connectivity, and long-term confidentiality requirements. The framework combines security-by-design principles with three migration patterns—drop-in replacement, hybrid protocol design, and protocol redesign—to guide the transition from classical to quantum-safe architectures. At the same time, simple substitution provides initial compatibility, hybrid and redesigned protocols with careful algorithm selection (ML-KEM, ML-DSA, FN-DSA, SLH-DSA), and optimizations better address URLLC and massive IoT constraints.

The framework is designed to be validated using a hybrid PQ-TLS prototype and a quantitative evaluation, as outlined in Section VII. At present, the Architectural Impact Matrix and 6G KPI Envelope are informed by literature and analytical reasoning; future measurements from actual implementations will further refine and validate these artifacts.

As this work focuses on a conceptual framework and evaluation methodology, future work will implement the proposed

TABLE IV: 6G KPI Envelope (Standardized Targets and Architectural Sensitivity to Proposed PQC Framework)

6G Metric	Typical Target Range (Literature Consensus)	Architectural Sensitivity to the Proposed PQC Framework
URLLC End-to-End (E2E) latency	< 1–10 ms end-to-end for mission-critical services (1 ms target with 99.999% reliability in many use cases) [32]	PQC handshakes (e.g., PQ-TLS, PQ-IKEv2) increase setup latency and consume part of the strict URLLC budget; steady-state data plane largely unaffected when sessions are long-lived [22], [12]
mMTC payload size	10–200 bytes typical sensor/telemetry payloads; many Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN) and Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) 802.15.4 links use frames =<127 bytes with small application payloads [33]	Large PQ signatures and certificate chains can dominate small packets, making header overhead much larger than payload and reducing radio efficiency in mMTC slices [24], [34]
Control-plane overhead budget	Strict signalling overhead constraints in sliced 5G/6G networks; control-plane traffic must remain a small fraction of total resources to meet latency and reliability targets [32]	Hybrid PQ key exchange and enlarged certificate objects in TLS/IKEv2 increase control-plane message sizes and setup signalling, tightening overhead budgets for 6G slicing and mobility procedures [22]
Device memory (IoT class)	Resource-constrained IoT nodes typically provide from a few kB to a few hundred kB of RAM and =<512 kB–1 MB of flash/storage [34]	Large PQ keys, signatures, and intermediate states may exceed RAM/flash limits on C0–C2-class Microcontroller Unit (MCU)s, necessitating lightweight PQC profiles, hardware offload, or protocol compression at the edge [24], [34]

hybrid PQ-TLS / PQ-IKEv2 designs and carry out the quantitative evaluation plan defined in Sections VI and VII. Future research will extend empirical evaluation to additional protocols, including MQTT, CoAP, and OPC UA, alongside more aggressive URLLC settings and realistic 6G testbeds. Formal verification using Tamarin or ProVerif will target the specific hybrid handshakes and downgrade protections developed in this work. Further development of lightweight, hardware-optimized PQC variants, compositional verification of hybrid certificate systems, and comprehensive multi-vendor interoperability testing will ensure scalability, reliability, and adaptability across URLLC, eMBB, and mMTC slices in complex 6G deployments.

X. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by Horizon Europe Evolution in Security and Privacy for 6G Networks (ENSURE-6G) Project (grant no. 101182933).

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Zhang, J. Wang, J. Lai, M. Dong, Z. Zhu, R. Ma, and J. Yang, “Research on development progress and test evaluation of post-quantum cryptography,” *Entropy*, vol. 27, no. 2, p. 212, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/e27020212>
- [2] A. Mutlugun, Y. Hanna, and K. Akkaya, “Performance evaluation of quantum-resistant ikev2 protocol for satellite networking environments,” in *2024 IEEE Virtual Conference on Communications (VCC)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–7. [Online]. Available: [10.1109/VCC63113.2024.10914395](https://doi.org/10.1109/VCC63113.2024.10914395)

- [3] C. De Alwis, A. Kalla, Q.-V. Pham, P. Kumar, K. Dev, W.-J. Hwang, and M. Liyanage, "Survey on 6g frontiers: Trends, applications, requirements, technologies and future research," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 2, pp. 836–886, 2021. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/OJCOMS.2021.3071496
- [4] S. Chen, Y.-C. Liang, S. Sun, S. Kang, W. Cheng, and M. Peng, "Vision, requirements, and technology trend of 6g: How to tackle the challenges of system coverage, capacity, user data-rate and movement speed," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 218–228, 2020. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/MWC.001.1900333
- [5] A. A. Shamsabadi, A. Yadav, Y. Gadallah, and H. Yanikomeroglu, "Exploring the 6g potentials: Immersive, hyperreliable, and low-latency communication," *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, 2025. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/MVT.2025.3531346
- [6] H. Tataria, M. Shafi, A. F. Molisch, M. Dohler, H. Sjöland, and F. Tufvesson, "6g wireless systems: Vision, requirements, challenges, insights, and opportunities," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 109, no. 7, pp. 1166–1199, 2021. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/JPROC.2021.3061701
- [7] C. K. Gitonga, "The impact of quantum computing on cryptographic systems: Urgency of quantum-resistant algorithms and practical applications in cryptography," *European Journal of Information Technologies and Computer Science*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.24018/compute.2025.5.1.146>
- [8] S.-J. Chen and Y.-H. Tsai, "Quantum-safe networks for 6g: An integrated survey on pqc, qkd, and satellite qkd with future perspectives," *Computing&AI Connect*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.69709/CAIC.2025.102135>
- [9] K. K. Vaigandla, "Quantum-secure iot networks for the 6g era: Post-quantum cryptography, blockchain integration, and trust architectures-a comprehensive review," *Journal of Sensors, IoT & Health Sciences (JSIHS, ISSN: 2584-2560)*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 44–75, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.69996/jsihs.2025014>
- [10] P. Udughapattuwa, C. De Alwis, E. Zeydan, U. Wijewardhana, and M. Liyanage, "Quantum-resistant security for blockchain-enabled 6g networks: A comprehensive review," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, 2026. [Online]. Available: DOI:10.1109/OJCOMS.2026.3673993
- [11] T. Attema, B. de Kock, S. M. Jayaprakash, D. Schoinianakis, T. Sijpesteijn, and R. van de Vlasakker, "Post-quantum cryptography in the 5g core," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2512.20243*, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2512.20243>
- [12] P. Kampanakis and W. Childs-Klein, "The impact of data-heavy, post-quantum tls 1.3 on the time-to-last-byte of real-world connections," *Cryptology ePrint Archive*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://dx.doi.org/10.14722/madweb.2024.23010>
- [13] T. Reddy, K. T. Hollebeek, J. Gray, and S. Fluhrer, "Use of SLH-DSA in TLS 1.3," Internet Engineering Task Force, Internet-Draft draft-reddy-tls-slhdsa-02, Nov. 2025, work in Progress. [Online]. Available: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-reddy-tls-slhdsa/02/>
- [14] B. Benčina, B. Dowling, V. Maram, and K. Xagawa, "Post-quantum cryptographic analysis of ssh," in *2025 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2025, pp. 595–613. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/SP61157.2025.00126
- [15] J. Señor, J. Portilla, and M. Portela-García, "Performance analysis of postquantum cryptographic schemes for securing large-scale wireless sensor networks," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 2024. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/TII.2024.3423315
- [16] "Post-quantum cryptography and the quantum future of cybersecurity," *Physical review applied*, vol. 21, no. 4, p. 040501, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevApplied.21.040501>
- [17] N. Ahmed, L. Zhang, and A. Gangopadhyay, "A survey of post-quantum cryptography support in cryptographic libraries," in *2025 IEEE International Conference on Quantum Computing and Engineering (QCE)*, vol. 1. IEEE, 2025, pp. 906–917. [Online]. Available: DOI:10.1109/QCE65121.2025.00102
- [18] S. Hoque, A. Aydeger, E. Zeydan, and M. Liyanage, "Analysis of post-quantum cryptography in user equipment in 5g and beyond," in *2025 IEEE 50th Conference on Local Computer Networks (LCN)*. IEEE, 2025, pp. 1–9. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/LCN65610.2025.11146323
- [19] E. Crockett, C. Paquin, and D. Stebila, "Prototyping post-quantum and hybrid key exchange and authentication in tls and ssh," *Cryptology ePrint Archive*, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://eprint.iacr.org/2019/858>
- [20] T. N. Turnip, B. Andersen, and C. Vargas-Rosales, "Towards 6g authentication and key agreement protocol: A survey on hybrid post quantum cryptography," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 2025. [Online]. Available: DOI:10.1109/COMST.2025.3567439
- [21] K. Tayef Shahriar and I. H. Sarker, "Exploring a hybrid deep learning framework to automatically discover topic and sentiment in covid-19 tweets," *arXiv e-prints*, pp. arXiv–2312, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.01178>
- [22] R. Rios, J. A. Montenegro, A. Muoz, and D. Ferraris, "Toward the quantum-safe web: Benchmarking post-quantum tls," *IEEE Network*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 247–253, 2025. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/MNET.2025.3531116
- [23] G. Tasopoulos, J. Li, A. P. Fournaris, R. K. Zhao, A. Sakzad, and R. Steinfeld, "Performance evaluation of post-quantum tls 1.3 on resource-constrained embedded systems," in *International Conference on Information Security Practice and Experience*. Springer, 2022, pp. 432–451. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21280-2_24
- [24] J. Blanco-Romero, V. Lorenzo, F. Almenares, D. D. Sánchez, C. Campo, and C. G. Rubio, "Integrating post-quantum cryptography into coap and mqtt-sn protocols," in *2024 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–6. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/ISCC61673.2024.10733716
- [25] S. Bae, Y. Chang, H. Park, M. Kim, and Y. Shin, "A performance evaluation of ipsec with post-quantum cryptography," in *International Conference on Information Security and Cryptology*. Springer, 2022, pp. 249–266. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-29371-9_13
- [26] P. Kampanakis, "Post-Quantum TLS 1.3 and SSH Performance (preliminary results) — blogs.cisco.com," <https://blogs.cisco.com/security/tls-ssh-performance-pq-kem-auth>, [Accessed 08-02-2026].
- [27] S. Ben, R. Adam, and D. Geest, "Use of the ml-dsa signature algorithm in the cryptographic message syntax (cms)," *Internet Engineering Task Force, Internet-Draft draftietf-lamps-cms-ml-dsa-06*, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.17487/RFC9882>
- [28] J.-A. Septien-Hernandez, M. Arellano-Vazquez, M. A. Contreras-Cruz, and J.-P. Ramirez-Paredes, "A comparative study of post-quantum cryptosystems for internet-of-things applications," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 2, p. 489, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22020489>
- [29] C. McLoughlin, C. Grietti, and J. Samandari, "Full post-quantum datagram tls handshake in the internet of things," in *International Conference on Codes, Cryptology, and Information Security*. Springer, 2023, pp. 57–76. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-33017-9_4
- [30] N. Bindel, C. Cremers, and M. Zhao, "Fido2, ctap 2.1, and webauthn 2: Provable security and post-quantum instantiation," in *2023 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1471–1490. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/SP46215.2023.10179454
- [31] P. Dobias, L. Malina, and J. Hajny, "Efficient unified architecture for post-quantum cryptography: combining dilithium and kyber," *PeerJ Computer Science*, vol. 11, p. e2746, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.2746>
- [32] A. Pourkabirian, M. S. Kordafshari, A. Jindal, and M. H. Anisi, "A vision of 6g urlhc: Physical-layer technologies and enablers," *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 20–27, 2024. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/MCOMSTD.0003.2300018
- [33] C. Bockelmann, N. K. Pratas, G. Wunder, S. Saur, M. Navarro, D. Gregoratti, G. Vivier, E. De Carvalho, Y. Ji, Č. Stefanović *et al.*, "Towards massive connectivity support for scalable mmte communications in 5g networks," *IEEE access*, vol. 6, pp. 28 969–28 992, 2018. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2837382
- [34] V. A. Thakor, M. A. Razzaque, and M. R. Khandaker, "Lightweight cryptography algorithms for resource-constrained iot devices: A review, comparison and research opportunities," *IEEE access*, vol. 9, pp. 28 177–28 193, 2021. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3052867